

Is the world real?

NO.

**Everything is just signals, a
sequence of numbers
following certain rules.**

From that, everything in this world is formed: from the fundamental forces of the universe, the physical laws, the cosmic rules of operation, to biology, philosophy, astrology, the I Ching, the Five Elements, etc.

And since it is signals, in my intuition, there must be a smallest unit (the smallest distance). I call this unit the constant G (not the gravitational constant).

This constant will explain many things. Here, I will give a few examples.

First is Zeno's paradox. I take the "dichotomy paradox" as the typical case to explain, because the other paradoxes such as Achilles and the tortoise are essentially similar.

**The dichotomy paradox is as follows:
“A motion must reach the halfway point before it can reach the end” (Wikipedia). That is, a person keeps going through half of the distances $1/2$, $1/4$, $1/8$, $1/16$, etc., and so will never reach the destination.**

In fact, it is impossible to keep dividing by 2 forever. At some point, it must stop—that is, when it reaches the smallest unit, the constant G.

That means the distance that person travels is just a finite number of times of the smallest unit, not infinite. Therefore, the person will reach the destination.

There was an explanation that a finite result could come from a sum of infinite decreasing elements. But an asymptote is just an asymptote, it can never be equal; $1.0000\dots000\dots1$ can never equal 1.

This is also the limitation of mathematics when explaining the world, or we can say mathematics is trying to explain something that, from the moment the concepts were introduced, was not completely in line with reality.

For example: repeating decimals (such as $1/3$). In fact, to explain the world, there is no such thing as infinity. Repeating many times will also reach the limit—that is, when it reaches the smallest unit, the constant G.

Likewise, there is no such thing as a non-repeating infinite decimal, like Pi. In the future, scientists will discover that Pi is also just a finite number. It's just that today people have not yet found all of its decimals, and if more are found, they are just meaningless digits to the world.

Another example: the speed of light is the fastest speed in the universe. Correct. Because light must pass through countless constants G. And in the material world, this is the fastest speed.

Quantum entanglement is different, because it is simply two different sequences of numbers operating correspondingly. And why do they operate correspondingly? Because they are connected in another dimension.

Or, the smallest particle known today is the quark (according to current physics). Some will say that in the future humans may discover smaller and smaller particles. In fact, at some point, there can be no smaller particles anymore, because that would already reach the constant G . It is impossible to go smaller forever.

By the way, I also want to share my view about Gödel's theorem: "Anything you draw a circle around cannot explain itself without referring to something outside the circle." Here, I am not discussing whether the theorem is right or wrong, because of course it has been proven correct.

The question I raise is: why do you draw the circle? Or, if this circle cannot explain itself without referring to a point outside the circle, then why not a bigger circle? A smaller circle that does not include the outside point and must refer to it—that is correct.

A logical system, if limited, of course cannot explain itself without going through a point outside the limit. So then, expand its limit.

For example, mathematics can always connect with other sciences such as physics and philosophy to form mathematics at a higher level.

These are just a few personal views that I want to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.